

The use of non-institutional email addresses in retracted publications with special attention to mass retractions due to fraudulent peer review

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The explosion of cases of peer review fraud and activities of paper mills pose a systemic threat to the integrity of the scientific publishing process. By linking the Retraction Watch and Web of Science databases, metadata of retracted publications are analysed. In the period 2004-2020, the use of non-institutional email addresses by reprint authors of retracted publications increased nearly fourfold, rising to over 65%. This increase was primarily driven by a much larger rise among authors with an affiliation in India and, especially, China. However, in the following two years the use of non-institutional email addresses decreased to its 2010 level. Among the journals with the most retracted publications, the use of non-institutional email addresses by reprint authors differs greatly: from 10 to 90%. Interestingly, only 28% of the mainly Chinese reprint authors of the mass retracted publications in Hindawi journals used a non-institutional email address, which contributed to the overall decline in the use of non-institutional email addresses in the 2020-2022 period. These results indicate that caution is recommended and not to automatically red-flag publications as fraudulent when non-institutional email addresses are used.

1. Introduction

One of the cornerstones of scientific research and public support in knowledge creation is trust in the academic publication process. Honest errors in data analysis and experimental procedures by authors or mistakes by editors and publishers are unavoidable and may pass unnoticed even the most rigorous peer review process and in a later stage result in the retraction of publications.

However, scientific misconduct turns out to be the main course of retractions. As illustrated by Hesselmann et al. (2017), until ten years ago the majority of the cases can be classified as fabrication or falsification of data or images and plagiarism (FFP). In recent years, the publication process itself became under growing pressure by two new forms of systemic manipulation: fraudulent peer-review (FPR) and activities of paper mills. In committing FPR, email addresses play an important role (Rivera & Teixeira da Silva, 2021). If the journal invites the authors to suggest reviewers, they may provide fake email addresses and the request to review the manuscript may be directed to one of the authors or to persons or organizations involved in the scam. Even the editorial process itself may be affected: editors, especially guest editors may be unable to find enough reviewers and hide the fact they provided many reviews themselves behind fake email addresses (Misra et al, 2018; Kincaid, 2023a). First identified in 2009, Vuong et al. (2020) found that in the period till 2019, FPR was the most common reason for retraction. In BioMed Central journals in the period 2000-2015, FPR did not occur as a retraction reason before 2014, but turned out to be by far and large the most common reason in 2015 (Moylan & Kowalczyk, 2016).

Paper mills are for-profit organizations that on a large scale produce and sell fraudulent manuscripts including fake data to provide the impression of genuine research products. They may also handle the submission for peer review (COPE & STM, 2022) and commit the above

described fraudulent acts. Another modus operandi of paper mills is to sell authorships after a manuscript has been accepted for publication in a bona fide scientific journal (Candal-Pedreira et al., 2022).

In efforts to address fraudulent activity, it is therefore not surprising that email addresses used in the publication process came under scrutiny. One of the indicators suggested as a red flag for fake or fraudulent publications is the use of non-institutional email addresses that can be obtained by anyone from public email service providers (Sabel et al., 2023; Brainard, 2023).

In this paper, the email addresses of the corresponding authors in the byline of retracted publications are analyzed. Section 2 describes the method and the data sources. The results are presented in section 3. The concluding section provides the contribution to the ongoing debate on vulnerabilities within the scientific publication process.

2. Data and methods

To study the use of email addresses by authors of retracted publications, we combined data from the Retraction Watch (RW) database and the Web of Science (WoS) database.

The RW database is a curated, searchable database of thousands of retractions. It offers detailed information, including author names, journal titles, and reasons for retraction. The database was initially managed by the Center for Scientific Integrity, the organization behind the Retraction Watch blog. In 2023, the database was acquired by Crossref, a non-profit organization focused on making research easy to find, cite, link, assess, and reuse. Crossref makes the database freely accessible (Hendricks et al., 2023).

A download of the RW database was made on June 5, 2024 through Crossref's Labs API (Hendricks et al., 2023). For this analysis the relevant fields in its records are: *OriginalPaperDOI*; *Journal*; *Publisher*; *OriginalPaperDate*; *RetractionDate*; *RetractionNature*; *Reason*; and *URLS* (Crossref, 2024; Retraction Watch, 2024). Most fields are self-explaining. In several cases a retraction is preceded by other actions such as the publication of a correction or after the publication of the associated retraction notice additional information came available. This information and the corresponding dates are stored in the fields *RetractionNature* and *RetractionDate*. The data in the field *Reason* is a string listing the various factors, separated by a semicolon, leading to the decision to retract a publication. The field *URLS* contains information used by the database managers in their communication about some cases.

For the analysis presented in this paper, for each *OriginalPaperDOI* the field *Reason* was split. The individual reasons and their order in the string were stored in a separate table.

The *OriginalPaperDOI* in the RW database was used to match the items in this database with the DOI in the in-house version of the WoS database, available at the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University. This search was limited to publications classified as 'article' and 'review' and with for the reprint author(s)¹ in the byline an email address.

Not all *OriginalPaperDOIs* in the RW database are from retracted items. For instance, for some publications a correction or an expression of concern is issued. To identify the retracted

¹ Corresponding authors are referred to in the WoS as reprint authors.

publications, a search was done for the word ‘Retraction’ in the field *RetractionNature*. In case in the field *RetractionDate* the corresponding date was not the most recent one, the *OriginalPaperDOI* was used to verify manually that the publication was indeed retracted on the date mentioned. Based on the most recent information, it turned out that only in two cases at a more recent date the retraction was invalidated and these cases were discarded in the analysis. The resulting set of publications is hereinafter referred to as ‘retracted publications’.

To analyze the distribution of the countries mentioned in the reprint authors’ addresses of the retracted publications, a counting scheme must be adopted. Several models are possible (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2024). In this preliminary analysis, each country mentioned in an address of a reprint author has been given a weight of 1. This means that a publication signed by a reprint author with multiple addresses from different countries is assigned with a weight of 1 for each country.

To analyze the use of email addresses by the reprint authors of retracted publications, the same counting scheme was used. Using the method described in Luwel & Van Eck (2023), the domain name in the reprint authors’ email address was assigned to a scholarly organization (institutional) or an email service provider (non-institutional).

The RW database also contains the name of the journal publishers of the retracted publications (in the field *Publisher*). For some publishers several names or acronyms were found and over time name changes occurred due to mergers and acquisitions. Using the most recent name, a unification was made with one exception. Hindawi, one of the largest publishers of peer-reviewed, fully open access journals, and only in 2021 acquired by Wiley, was analyzed separately because of the mass retractions of thousands of its publications.

In the analysis, special attention was paid to publications in Hindawi journals that were in bulk retracted due to signs of manipulated peer review. Information about these fraudulent cases was published in the Retraction Watch blog posts: ‘Exclusive: Hindawi and Wiley to retract over 500 papers linked to peer review rings’ (Kincaid, 2022), ‘Wiley and Hindawi to retract 1,200 more papers for compromised peer review’ (Kincaid, 2023b), and , ‘Hindawi reveals process for retracting more than 8,000 paper mill articles. Retraction Watch’ (Kincaid, 2023c). We selected the retracted Hindawi publications by identifying all retractions that contain a link to these blog posts in the *URLS* field.²

3. Results

This section presents the results of our analysis of retracted publications, identified according to the methodology described in Section 2. The analysis specifically focuses on retracted publications from the RW database that are classified in the WoS as articles or reviews and for which the email address of the reprint author is available.

The results are presented in two subsections. In the first subsection, we present some general characteristics of retracted publications and provide more specific results on the use of email addresses by their reprint authors. In the second subsection, we present a case study on the mass retraction of Hindawi publications due to signs of manipulated peer review processes.

² In the *URLS* field, we search for ‘500’ or ‘1200’ or ‘8000’ and ensured no double counting occurred. As Wiley acquired Hindawi in 2021, similar searches were performed for Wiley retracted papers, but these turned out to be negative.

3.1. Characteristics of retracted publications and the usage of institutional and non-institutional email addresses by reprint authors

Retracted publications in the period 2004-2023

In Table 1, the number of retracted publications by their original publication year is given. Between 2004 and 2020, a gradual increase is observed. Between 2020 and 2023 the number of retracted publications more than doubled. The relatively low count for 2023 could be explained by the retraction of publications after June 5, 2024, the date at which the RW database was downloaded.

Table 1 also includes for each publication year the average delay between the retraction date and the publication date, further called retraction delay. For 329 retracted publications, the retraction date is identical to the publication date. Either this is due to errors in databases or missing information about the retraction date. These cases were considered to be outliers and were not taken further into account in the analysis. The retraction delay reduces from more than four year at the end of the first decade of this century to around two years at the end of the next decade. For 2022 and 2023, the most recent years, the delay could be underestimated as publications may be retracted after the download of the RW database was done.

For all retracted publications in the period 2004-2023, we found that 50.9% of the reprint authors used a non-institutional and 48.7% an institutional email address. The domain name of 0.4% of the email addresses could not be assigned to one of those categories. However, a clear increasing trend in the usage of non-institutional email addresses is visible in Table 1. In the period 2004-2008, 26% of the reprint authors used a non-institutional email address while this number increased to 58% in the period 2018-2022³.

Table 2a shows the top 20 countries mentioned in the reprint authors' addresses of the retracted publications as well as their fraction in the total number of retracted publications. Although only based on the reprint authors' addresses, it is obvious that for some countries the share of retracted publications is much higher than their overall share of publications in WoS. This is especially true for China, India, and Iran.

In the type of email address, the difference among the 20 countries with the most retracted publications is very large (Table 2a). For China reprint authors use a non-institutional email address in retracted publications more than twice as frequently than an institutional one. For India it is even fourfold. For the Global West countries the percentage of non-institutional email addresses is 26% or below.

The distribution of retracted papers over the publishers is highly concentrated, with a Gini index of 0.93. The top 10 publishers cover 80% of all retracted publications (Table 3), with the top three publishers alone contributing to more than half. Hindawi's prominent position is largely explained by the bulk retraction of publications in recent years (see Section 3.2). The substantial position of Springer Nature and Elsevier should not be surprising as these two conglomerates publish a comparable proportion of all the publications in WoS. Looking at the use of email addresses by reprint authors, we see that 70% of Hindawi's reprint authors use institutional email addresses. On the other hand, for Wolter Kluwer (67%), Taylor and Francis (70%) and especially Spandidos (94%) the reprint authors prefer non-institutional email addresses.

³ The year 2023 is excluded here since its value must be handled with some precaution.

Table 1: Characteristics of retracted publications and the usage of institutional and non-institutional email addresses by reprint authors of these retracted publications in the period 2004-2023.

pub. year	# retracted publications	avg. retraction delay in months	email addresses of reprint authors		
			% institutional	% non-institutional	% unknown
2004	232	92.9	82.8	17.2	0.0
2005	322	85.8	77.5	21.6	0.9
2006	414	73.7	75.7	23.6	0.7
2007	519	63.4	60.0	39.8	0.2
2008	475	59.9	70.3	29.3	0.4
2009	534	55.3	68.8	30.9	0.3
2010	583	51.5	66.6	32.8	0.6
2011	657	54.3	70.0	29.6	0.4
2012	792	45.0	65.0	34.9	0.1
2013	840	52.2	61.1	38.6	0.3
2014	1,000	45.2	48.9	50.9	0.3
2015	1,002	44.1	45.0	54.7	0.3
2016	969	39.0	45.5	54.4	0.1
2017	1,096	37.2	39.7	60.2	0.1
2018	1,404	34.2	37.7	62.3	0.1
2019	1,881	29.4	30.8	69.1	0.1
2020	1,982	23.3	33.7	65.7	0.6
2021	3,106	20.4	42.5	57.0	0.4
2022	5,128	13.1	65.9	33.5	0.6
2023	529	11.9	45.0	54.3	0.8

Table 2a: Top 20 countries most mentioned in the addresses of reprint authors of retracted publications in the period 2004-2023.

country	# retracted publications	% of all retracted publications	% email addresses of reprint authors		
			institutional	non-institutional	unknown
China	12,333	51.4	39.7	60.2	0.2
United States	2,338	9.7	89.7	10.0	0.3
India	1,626	6.8	19.1	80.8	0.1
Iran	813	3.4	59.3	40.4	0.2
Japan	575	2.4	81.5	18.1	0.3
South Korea	521	2.2	79.2	20.4	0.4
United Kingdom	416	1.7	84.6	15.2	0.2
Saudi Arabia	364	1.5	52.9	47.1	0.0
Egypt	363	1.5	28.6	71.1	0.3
Pakistan	354	1.5	44.4	55.6	0.0
Italy	329	1.4	75.1	22.5	2.4
Germany	313	1.3	73.3	26.1	0.6
Taiwan	247	1.0	80.6	19.0	0.4
Ethiopia	224	0.9	72.4	27.6	0.0
Australia	223	0.9	87.4	12.6	0.0
Malaysia	197	0.8	63.0	36.0	0.9
Turkey	193	0.8	47.2	52.8	0.0
Spain	185	0.8	75.1	24.3	0.5
France	183	0.8	76.1	23.9	0.0
Canada	180	0.7	79.0	21.0	0.0

Table 2b: Top 20 countries most mentioned in the addresses of reprint authors of retracted publications in the period 2019-2023.

country	# retracted publications	% of all retracted publications	% email addresses of reprint authors		
			institutional	non-institutional	unknown
China	8,849	66.5	45.8	54.0	0.2
India	949	7.1	18.3	81.6	0.1
United States	473	3.6	80.0	19.2	0.8
Saudi Arabia	290	2.2	57.4	42.6	0.0
Pakistan	283	2.1	43.2	56.8	0.0
Iran	239	1.8	57.3	42.7	0.0
Ethiopia	226	1.7	72.2	27.8	0.0
South Korea	193	1.4	77.0	23.0	0.0
Egypt	185	1.4	49.5	50.5	0.0
United Kingdom	104	0.8	80.4	19.6	0.0
Malaysia	100	0.8	72.1	26.0	1.9
Turkey	96	0.7	45.0	55.0	0.0
Japan	76	0.6	83.7	15.2	1.1
Russia	73	0.5	21.1	65.8	13.2
Australia	72	0.5	81.0	19.0	0.0
Germany	70	0.5	80.8	19.2	0.0
Taiwan	63	0.5	77.1	22.9	0.0
Vietnam	51	0.4	93.2	6.8	0.0
Italy	49	0.4	75.0	25.0	0.0
Spain	47	0.4	70.6	29.4	0.0

Table 3: Top 10 publishers with the largest number of retracted publications in the period 2004-2023.

publisher	# retracted publications	% of all retracted publications	% email addresses of reprint authors		
			institutional	non-institutional	unknown
Hindawi	5,356	22.8	69.6	30.1	0.3
Springer Nature	4,130	17.6	38.7	60.6	0.6
Elsevier	3,287	14.0	53.2	46.5	0.3
Wiley	1,767	7.5	45.2	54.0	0.8
Taylor and Francis	1,636	7.0	29.8	70.0	0.2
SAGE Publications	746	3.2	39.5	60.1	0.4
PLoS	632	2.7	48.8	51.0	0.1
Spandidos	503	2.1	6.2	93.6	0.2
Wolters Kluwer	341	1.5	33.2	66.8	0.0
Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC)	247	1.1	46.6	53.4	0.0

The distribution of the retracted publications over the journals is also concentrated but with a Gini Index of 0.49 less than for the publishers. The 20 journals with the most retracted publications contain 26% of the total number (Table 4) and 54% of the journals have only one publication retracted. Among the top journals the use of institutional email addresses varies widely, even among journals of the same publisher.

Comparison between retracted and non-retracted publications in the period 2019-2023

For the period 2019-2023, Luwel & Van Eck (2025) analyzed the usage of email addresses by reprint authors in 13.2 million articles and reviews included in the WoS.⁴ 72% of the reprint authorships with an email were identified as institutional, 25% as non-institutional, and 3% could not be assigned to a category. Compared to the retracted publications collected in this study there are large differences. For the same period, only 43% of the reprint authors of retracted publications used an institutional and 56% a non-institutional email address. Based on these findings, we can conclude that the use of non-institutional email addresses in retracted publications is much higher than in non-retracted publications. Since we found that China is overrepresented in retracted publications and the observation that the use of non-institutional email addresses by Chinese reprint authors is much more common (Luwel & Van Eck, 2023), we performed also a more detailed comparison at the country level.

Table 2b provides for the period 2019-2023 the top 20 countries most mentioned in the addresses of reprint authors of retracted publications. As could be expected, compared to Table 2a (which is based on the period 2004-2023) for each country the number is lower and the ranking of countries differ somewhat. China is still at the top, but India as second has twice the number of retracted publications of the United States, which is at third place. Ethiopia takes the place of Japan in the top 10. For 6 of the top 10 countries, the difference with the values for the period 2004-2023 is less than 6%, except for United States with a decrease of 10% in the use of institutional email addresses and an increase by 20% for Egypt. For the countries starting with Malaysia, the number of retracted publications and email addresses in the period 2019-2023 is rather small and the changes must be interpreted with some care.

Of the top 10 countries mentioned in Table 2b, 7 countries are also included in Figure 6 of Luwel & Van Eck (2025). Due to the low number of WoS publications, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and Ethiopia are not mentioned in Figure 6 of Luwel and Van Eck (2025). For the 7 countries included in both studies, we were able to make a comparison between the usage of institutional and non-institutional email addresses by reprint authors of retracted publications and non-retracted publications. For China and India, the fraction of non-institutional email addresses is considerably higher for the retracted publication than for the WoS publications.

⁴ Retracted publications were also part of their analysis, but the number of retracted publications is neglectable to the overall number publications in WoS.

Table 4: Top 20 journals with the largest number of retracted publications in the period 2004-2023.

journal	publisher	# retracted publications	% email addresses of reprint authors		
			institutional	non-institutional	unknown
Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience	Hindawi	634	86.6	12.8	0.6
PLoS One	PLoS	608	48.3	51.5	0.1
Journal of Healthcare Engineering	Hindawi	497	69.2	30.3	0.6
Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing	Hindawi	467	89.7	9.9	0.4
Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine	Hindawi	459	16.4	83.0	0.6
Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine	Hindawi	450	54.2	45.6	0.2
Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing	Springer Nature	301	17.4	82.6	0.0
Security and Communication Networks	Hindawi	272	89.0	11.0	0.0
Journal of Environmental and Public Health	Hindawi	270	88.6	11.4	0.0
The Journal of Biological Chemistry	ASBMB	251	93.7	5.9	0.4
Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews	Wiley	215	63.7	35.8	0.5
OncoTargets and Therapy	Taylor and Francis	210	9.0	91.0	0.0
Advances in Materials Science and Engineering	Hindawi	201	74.7	25.3	0.0
Journal of Cellular Biochemistry	Wiley	200	9.5	90.5	0.0
BioMed Research International	Hindawi	194	51.6	48.4	0.0
Mathematical Problems in Engineering	Hindawi	190	78.5	21.0	0.5
Scientific Reports	Springer Nature	189	55.2	44.4	0.4
RSC Advances	RSC	173	26.0	74.0	0.0
The International Journal of Electrical Engineering & Education	SAGE Publications	166	26.6	73.4	0.0
Mobile Information Systems	Hindawi	165	89.2	9.6	1.2

3.2. Manipulated peer reviews and retracted Hindawi publications

The downloaded version of the RW database contains the metadata of 5,356 publications with Hindawi as publisher (Table 3). Using the search strategy described in Section 2, we identified 5,040 (94%) Hindawi publications that were mass retracted because of signs of manipulated peer reviews. These are subsequently referred to as ‘mass retracted Hindawi publications’.

Analyzing the field *Reason*, of the 5,040 in mass retracted Hindawi publications, it is not surprising that ‘Investigation by Journal/Publisher’ and ‘Concerns/Issues with Peer Review’ were most frequently mentioned as reason.

Table 5 gives an overview of the mass retracted Hindawi publications by publication year and by retraction year: 98% were published in 2021 and a large majority was already retracted in 2023. As the database was downloaded on June 5, 2024, is it possible more publications are retracted but not included in the analysis.

Table 5: Number of mass retracted Hindawi publications by publication year (left) and retraction year (right).

publication year	# retracted publications	% of all retracted publications	retraction year	# retracted publications	% of all retracted publications
2020	49	1.0	2022	297	5.9
2021	921	18.3	2023	4,464	88.6
2022	4,042	80.2	2024	279	5.5
2023	26	0.5	Total	5,040	100.0
Total	5,040	100.0			

These mass retracted publications are predominantly from China: of the 5,484 reprint authors 4,693 (85,6%) have a Chinese address in the publications’ byline (Table 6). Additionally, as shown in Table 6, 71.5% of the reprint authors overall, as well as those with Chinese affiliations use an institutional email address.

Table 6: Usage of email addresses by reprint authors in mass retracted Hindawi publications.

	# email addresses of reprint authors			total
	institutional	non-institutional	unknown	
All reprint authors	3,919 (71.5%)	1,549 (28.2%)	16 (0.3%)	5,484 (100.0%)
Chinese reprint authors	3,356 (71.5%)	1,323 (28.2%)	14 (0.3%)	4,693 (100.0%)

The use of institutional email addresses by Chinese reprint authors is slightly higher for the mass-retracted publications compared to all publications indexed in the WoS (Luwel & Van Eck, 2025). However, it is 25% higher than for all retracted publications with a Chinese reprint author address published in the period 2019-2023 (Table 2b).

4. Conclusion

Using the June 2024 download of the RW database, the number of retracted publications in WoS increased steadily and grew more than eightfold in the period 2004-2020. Notably, the number of retracted publications in 2022 more than doubled compared to 2020. Between 2004 and 2020, the average retraction delay decreased by nearly six years. In the same period, the

use of non-institutional email addresses by reprint authors of retracted publications nearly quadrupled to more than 65%. During the period 2019-2023, non-institutional email addresses are two times more frequently used in retracted publications than in non-retracted publications in the WoS.

In line with results of earlier studies (Xiao et al., 2022), nearly 50% of the retracted publications have at least one reprint author from China. There are large differences among the countries with the most retracted publications in the use of non-institutional email addresses by reprint authors: for India 81% and China 60% but for the Global West countries only 26% or less. The former two countries are largely responsible for the above-mentioned difference in the use of email addresses between retracted and non-retracted publications.

Between journals, the use of non-institutional email addresses by reprint authors in retracted publications varies considerably (from 10% to 90%). Large differences are also found between journals from the same publisher.

In the case study of the mass retraction of publications by Hindawi, the most striking observation is certainly the relative low fraction of non-institutional email addresses (28%) notwithstanding that 86% of the reprint author mention China as country in the publications' byline.

Given the recent strong rise of FPR (e.g., Moylan & Kowalczyk, 2016) and the fact that the use of non-institutional email addresses is more common in retracted papers than in non-retracted papers (Luwel & Van Eck, 2023), we think it is justifiable to pay more attention during the review process to publications whose authors use non-institutional email addresses. However, based on the large differences we found in the usage of non-institutional email addresses among journals (of the same publisher) and the relative low fraction of non-institutional email addresses in the Hindawi mass retraction case study calls for caution to automatically 'red-flag' publications as fake or fraudulent whose authors use non-institutional email addresses. It is moreover important not to forget that institutional email addresses can be misused as well (Teixeira da Silva, 2022).

In ongoing research, the reasons for retractions are studied, with a distinction made between genuine errors and academic misconduct. Additionally, the usage of email addresses by reprint authors is analyzed separately for these two categories.

Open science practices

The Retraction Watch database, acquired by Crossref, is openly available (Hendricks et al., 2023). However, due to license restrictions, this is not the case for the data obtained from the WoS database used in the analysis. The source code used in the analysis of this paper to classify email addresses as institutional and non-institutional is available in the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/neesjanvaneck/WoS-email-address-analysis>.

Author contributions

Marc Luwel: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing—original draft. Nees Jan van Eck: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing—review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interest.

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